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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

Education and public outreach plays a larger role than ever before in science and astronomy. Canada’s 2017 Fundamental Science Review revealed that Canadians hold a mostly favourable opinion towards science, yet there is a fundamental divide between who they perceive as scientists and non-scientists. While Canadians like science, they do not feel engaged in the scientific process or community. Furthermore, our community is grappling with often unreliable sources of funding and the absence of a process which allows the granting of funding to big science projects. This is resulting in several missed opportunities in terms of Canadian-lead projects that are dying on the vine or having to bow out of collaborations with international partners.

In this white paper, we present a number of past advocacy and engagement initiatives that have attempted to increase and improve our visibility with the public which include the explosion of science communication initiatives in Canada and the lobbying activities of the Coalition for Canadian Astronomy. With the increasing presence and awareness of “fake news” and the like in the media, we believe that it is the perfect time to strike and push for more stable astronomy funding (including for EPO-specific programs), greater visibility for both our science and our scientists, and a better relationship with the Canadian public.

To improve the landscape of astronomy culture in Canada, we have the following recommendations to present to the LRP2020 Committee:

- 1) We recommend that CASCA hire a paid Press Officer that can assist CASCA members in disseminating their scientific results to the public and the media and help connect astronomers to science journalists across Canada and internationally. This position could be a part-time task folded into a full-time position that encompasses other duties (national EPO activities, administration, etc.) and would require increasing CASCA membership fees and/or exploring alternate means of funding (philanthropy, donations, fundraising, etc.). The duties of such a Press/EPO Officer could include the development resources such as workshops and cheat sheets that would enable astronomers to become better science communicators and advocates for Canadian astronomy and its societal benefits.
- 2) We recommend that physics and astronomy departments across Canada incorporate “soft skills” such as science communication and public speaking into their graduate curricula.
- 3) We recommend that the Coalition for Canadian Astronomy work closely with CASCA to develop and deliver a broader suite of astronomy advocacy and lobbying events on Parliament Hill.
- 4) We recommend that CASCA and its Board work on more deliberate collaborations between CASCA

and science centres as well as between CASCA and student astronomy clubs. This would include sending one or several CASCA members to the Canadian Association of Science Centres' annual conference, and inviting science centre professionals and members of astronomy student clubs to the EPO session of CASCA's annual meeting.

5) We recommend that federal funding agencies such as NSERC and CFI include EPO activities in their evaluation metrics and allow a portion of awarded funding to be used for EPO and communication activities.

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1 Introduction

Education and public outreach play a larger role than ever before in science worldwide. Several scientists such as Neil deGrasse Tyson and Bill Nye have solidified their celebrity status in pop culture. Scientific discoveries are made available to the public practically in realtime thanks to the internet and social media. With the rise of social media, along with prominent and diversified science communicators including science journalists, it appears that there has never been a better time to be perceived as a “geek”. Yet scientific endeavours find themselves woefully underfunded, governments are not prioritising fundamental research and a generalised distrust of scientists and science is sweeping parts of the world, including Canada.

Despite EPO becoming increasingly prioritised by our community, a gap between scientists and the general public (so-called “non-scientists”) remain. While Canada has been shown to have a healthy relationship with science and its scientists, this gap is unfortunately growing. Astronomy has proven itself time and time again to be a fantastic “gateway science” which invites typically disinterested individuals, especially youth, to learn more about science through the wonders of space. Our community is uniquely positioned to use our field to better engage Canadian citizens with science by reaching out to them using innovative and coordinated EPO practices.

As our scientific goals greatly depend on government funding, we must also learn to be better science advocates to voters, government officials, entrepreneurs and key decision-makers and stakeholders. Through activities such as lobbying and media interventions, astronomers stand to gain visibility, a privileged position in decision-making on matters of scientific interest among their peers and the Canadian scientific community at large, and finally a healthy trusting relationship with the public. Our community must imperatively use these platforms not only to highlight the intrinsic wonder and the innate curiosity associated with our field of work, but also all the societal and economic benefits attached. One cannot ignore the importance of lobbying in our community’s history. One notable example is John S. Plaskett’s successful bid to Canadian prime ministers Laurier and Borden to ensure the funding and construction of the Dominion Astrophysical Observatory in Victoria, B.C. which recently celebrated its centennial anniversary.

In this white paper, we hope to give an overview of astronomy advocacy and engagement as they stand in Canada and recommend strategies and tools that could be developed in the 2020s to better equip Canadian astronomers to perform advocacy and engagement. For more information on related EPO matters, we also suggest reading CASCA’s EPO Committee’s white paper, Langill et al.

2 Context

2.1 Science Culture in Canada

Several national and international studies have attempted to describe the state of science culture in the last decade. For its 2014 report *Science Culture: Where Canada Stands* (Carty et al., 2014), the Council of Canadian Academies defined a society with a strong science culture as one that embraces discovery, supports the use of scientific knowledge and methodology, and encourages the education and training of a highly skilled workforce and development of an innovative knowledge-based economy.

The report’s findings were mostly optimistic. Compared to several other countries included in the study, Canada was shown to have citizens that had few public reservations about science, were interested in new scientific discoveries, enjoyed visiting science centres and museums and demonstrated a good basic level of scientific literacy. This leads us to believe that Canadians are generally interested in and supportive of science. Performance indicators related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) skills development was much more variable, however. Only 20% of first university degrees granted in Canada were in a STEM field. This is made worse by the fact that there are half as many women opting for a STEM program as there are men according to a 2016 report by Statistics Canada (Statistics Canada, 2016). One might come to the general conclusion that, while Canadians like science, they do not feel they are part of the scientific process or community. Such a context can easily be twisted into an “us versus them” scenario, which may very well be what is eroding the general public’s trust in scientists, especially throughout the Western world.

For the second year in a row, the *3M State of Science Index* (3M, 2019) explored global attitudes towards science and revealed several interesting tensions in its polling results. Among other challenges, it would appear that a third of polled individuals were skeptical of science, and this percentage has only grown in the last year. When looking at the opinions of Canadians in this poll, attitudes towards science remain wholly positive and Canadians appear conscious of the importance and impact of science and technology in their daily lives. One unfortunate and jarring finding, however, is that 44% of Canadians find scientists elitists. Furthermore, the main reason given as to why Canadians are skeptical of science is that there are “too many conflicting opinions by scientists”. This underlines a lack of understanding on the public’s part of what the scientific process entails and poor communication on scientists’ part. This is likely made worse by the way scientific discoveries are reported in the media. Tentative results are often sold as absolutes, hyperbole is used to sensationalise headlines, and scientists can then appear to flip flop when more nuanced details come out afterwards. Finally, the report indicates that few Canadian respondents (only 9%) would pick physical sciences (including astronomy) when asked in which field they would start a new job now that would lead to a satisfying career. Compare this to 22% choosing business, 19% choosing education and teaching, and 18% each choosing information technology and medicine. Clearly, Canadians do not seem drawn to careers paths in the pure sciences.

Such reports identify both the strengths and weaknesses of science culture in Canada. Thankfully, they also indicate concrete steps that Canadian scientists can take to better connect with the public. These include:

- **Highlighting the scientists behind the science:** the general public is more engaged when there is a human component to the science story they are hearing, and showcasing scientists can help bridge the gap between the scientific community and the general public that breeds mistrust and a perception of elitism (Olson, 2009)
- **Improving scientists’ storytelling skills:** the general public can find scientific results confusing, all the more so if they are explained through jargon or are in direct conflict with other scientific results; scientists must hone their communication skills in order to better guide the public through science stories in an engaging manner
- **Answering the “so what?” question:** the general public becomes significantly more interested in science if it is relatable and makes sense in the context of their daily lives
- **Making science inclusive:** the general public can often feel like science is something you learn at school or is strictly for one “type” of person; by showcasing a range of different representations of scientists and by tailoring science engagement to different demographics (including adults) and new technologies, the general public can better see themselves as scientists too; science should be portrayed as a process that everyone can partake in, where simply asking the question “why?” connects someone to the scientific method

Findings reported here concern science broadly, as similar studies concerning astronomy in Canada are not currently available. That being said, it is a logical conclusion that the landscape of astronomy culture in Canada will be intimately tied to Canada’s science culture.

2.2 Astronomy Funding in Canada

Nurturing our nation’s science culture requires dedicated funding, not only for scientific projects but also for EPO initiatives which ensure that scientific discoveries are properly communicated to the public. The issue of astronomy funding in Canada has been included in both the 2000 and 2010 Long Range Plans. Canadian astronomy is funded through a number of agencies, organisations and institutes, including the National Research Council Canada (NRC-C), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC), the Canadian Space Agency (CSA), and the Canadian Foundation for Innovation (CFI) (see Sect. 6 of the LRP2010 for more details on the state of things as of a decade ago). While public agencies provide the key foundational funding for Canadian astronomy, additional funding from private companies or philanthropic benefactors are a welcomed additional supplement. The Canadian Institute for Advanced Research (CIFAR), the Dunlap Institute for Astronomy and Astrophysics (University of Toronto) and the Institute for Research on Exoplanets (Université de Montréal) all benefit from such funding with

varying degrees of permanence. In order to participate in large astronomy projects that require years if not decades of planning and engagement, our community requires years if not decades of secure funding.

Canadian astronomers have shown to be remarkably impactful on the international stage, and this is the case despite funding that is not keeping up with the standards of comparable countries. Canada's annual spending on astronomy as a relative fraction of GDP puts us 7th in the world behind countries such as Australia, the United States and France. The situation is particularly dire in space astronomy. Canada's 2009 civilian space budget as a relative fraction of GDP is only the 15th largest in the world behind Luxembourg. Lack of current funding, of a longterm funding strategy and of a broad base of funded astronomy projects has already lead to the erosion of trust between Canada and its international partners. The quickly-closing window of opportunity to participate in NASA's WFIRST mission is one example.

Canada's 2017 *Fundamental Science Review* (Naylor et al., 2017) indicates that these issues are generalised across most of our nation's scientific fields, but space astronomy-specific investigations such as the OECD's *Space and Innovation* study (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2016) report that Canada is losing ground on other countries at a particularly alarming rate in this field. Canada's recent history in space exploration is to adopt a risk averse approach, something that has been particularly hard hitting on the deep innovation sector in which astronomy technology development sits. Caiazza et al. (2017) goes into more detail on the necessary minimum funding and longterm fund allocation strategy for space astronomy in Canada to ensure its continuity. In a nutshell, however, Canada's space exploration falls short by about an order of magnitude both compared to other nations but also when looking at our community's needs. For outreach purposes, space-based astronomy is particularly intriguing to the public. The realisation of a project such as the CASTOR telescope (often described in shorthand as Canada's own Hubble Space Telescope, see Côté et al.'s white paper for more information) would be an unparalleled opportunity for astronomy EPO in Canada, an incredible tool to increase our public visibility and advocacy means and would surely become a landmark in Canada's astronomy heritage.

3 Past and Current Initiatives

The list of initiatives presented here is not meant to be exhaustive. Rather it should give our community a general indication of the current state of astronomy advocacy and engagement programs in Canada.

3.1 Science Communication Initiatives

A number of EPO activities have been carried out by CASCA members and the CASCA EPO Committee over the last decade. For a more complete description of these, please refer to Langill et al.'s white paper. In addition to these more nationwide events and activities, science communication has been put at the forefront of many astronomical institutions' mandates. The Dunlap Institute (University of Toronto), the McGill Space Institute (McGill University) and the Institute for Research of Exoplanets (Université de Montréal), to name a few, have all had in the past decade or currently have outreach staff who ensure the creation and delivery of EPO activities for the general public and for K-12 students. We also note the creation of the Science Outreach Centre at Saint-Mary's University in Halifax, NS.

Universities and various astronomical institutions have increased the time and resources they dedicate to communicating their astronomers' exciting results by writing a greater number of press releases, soliciting more media interviews for their scientists and by featuring their research highlights on platforms such as social media, institutional websites, etc. Many astronomers now consider the dissemination of their discoveries as part of their responsibilities as scientists (and as individuals who often benefit from Canadian citizens' tax dollars) and are more engaged with their local press officers or have built a relationship with science journalists across Canada. This is especially imperative as the number of journalists and writers who can dedicate their careers to science and technology has greatly dwindled in past years. Journalists who do cover space stories have been known to source their information from international press releases (especially from NASA) and obtain comments from non-Canadian astronomers, yet they are often keen to obtain a Canadian spin on their pieces. Supplying them with this information must be a continued effort.

A number of specific initiatives in Canada exist in the hope of strengthening the ties between scientists and the media. Some academic institutions such as York University have launched “Science Communicator in Residence” programs wherein a journalist or other science communicator works out of the Faculty of Science for several months to encourage bridge building between the scientific and communications communities. The Science Media Centre of Canada was also founded in 2008 to improve the quality and quantity of scientific media coverage throughout the nation. The federal government has even encouraged similar endeavours such as the “Research2Reality” project through funding via the NSERC PromoScience grant; this platform seeks to showcase Canadian scientists, the innovative work they do and the impact this work has on our daily lives.

There has been a veritable explosion of science communication workshops (e.g. Beakerhead, SciCommCamp, etc.), conferences (e.g. ComSciCon), associations (e.g. Science Writers and Communicators of Canada, Association des communicateurs scientifiques du Québec) and even university degrees (e.g. M.Sc. in Science Communication at Laurentian University, B.Sc. in Science Communication at Mount Saint-Vincent University, Science Communication Certificate at Seneca College, etc.) in Canada and worldwide in the last decade. While none are specifically targeted towards astronomers, many astronomers have benefited from participating in these opportunities. They allow the sharing of ideas and resources between scientists and communicators alike scattered across the country and promote collaboration across this network.

A few physics and astronomy departments across Canada have also started appreciating the importance of communicating one’s science in a clear, interesting and accessible manner. The inclusion of certain “soft skills” such as public speaking and media training are now being incorporated into graduate training in some of these universities. Beyond shaping students into better educators, these skills also prove immensely useful for proposal and grant writing, job interviews and general teamwork and collaboration. While there are currently no science communication workshops offered specifically to Canadian astronomers, many of them tune in to webinars given by organisations like the partially CASCA-funded *Discover the Universe* that are targeted to K-12 educators and the general public. These allow astronomers to see the level they should be targeting with their explanations and give concrete examples of the language and stories that can be used to engage broad audiences. While they are great examples to follow, they do not, however, explicitly discuss science communication methodology.

Finally, we are happy to note that science centres, museums and planetariums across Canada are reaching out to the scientific and astronomy communities more than ever. The three federal science museums in Ottawa, including the Canada Space and Aviation Museum, have all created Science Advisor positions that are held by Ph.D. level scientists. The Planétarium Rio Tinto Alcan de Montréal is preparing to launch its own research program akin to those at the American Museum of Natural History (New York) and the Adler Planetarium (Chicago) and is now showcasing the work of Montréal-based astronomers during very well-attended public talks. Regular sessions discussing how to better integrate scientists into science centres are held every year at the Canadian Association of Science Centres’ annual meeting. There is a definite desire on the part of science centres to become a platform for astronomers. The main barriers typically identified to these potential collaborations is a lack of time in the busy professional lives of astronomers and the lack of science communication training of these astronomers that is needed to bring them up to science centre standards.

In general, science communication is experiencing an exciting upswell all over Canada and astronomers, especially early-career astronomers, are at the forefront of this movement. Lack of time and resources, unfortunately, often stop astronomers from performing science communication despite their desire to. Furthermore, the fact that EPO activities are often not included in evaluation metrics for grants, tenure and academic positions mean that astronomers are often forced to deprioritise their EPO activities.

3.2 Coalition for Canadian Astronomy

The Coalition for Canadian Astronomy was formed following the release of the LRP2000. Its goal was to secure federal funding to support the projects endorsed by this LRP2000 and the LRP2010 following it. The Coalition itself draws representatives from the Association of Canadian Universities for Research in Astronomy (ACURA) as well as from industry and academia. Financial support from CASCA and ACURA have allowed the Coalition to lean on the help of Ottawa lobbying firm Temple Scott Associates for their activities on Parliament Hill.

In recent years, the Coalition's main messaging has centred on two main points:

- Create an official entity for funding applications for big science projects, and provide it with sufficient funding for Canadian researchers to take advantage of international collaboration opportunities
- Establish a new vision for the CSA that includes space science, with annual funding of \$100 million to support competitions for small, medium and large space missions

Emphasis has also been placed on CASCA's commitment to gender balance, diversity and EPO initiatives. Coalition members present astronomy as being Canada's top science during meetings with Members of Parliament (MPs) based on Canadian astronomers ranking first in the G7 in standard analyses of per capita impact. While astronomy is described as fundamentally in line with human curiosity and our need to understand the Universe, Coalition members are also briefed in the many critical innovations and significant economic spin-offs that have been made possible through astronomy. The deep innovation that allows society to gain technological advances several orders of magnitude improved from their predecessors is shown to only be possible through fundamental research such as astronomy.

Meetings with MPs have generally been quite positive, at least superficially. The great majority of them are unaware of most of the large projects headed by Canadian astronomers and many are surprised by our community's impact on the international stage. Most MPs are very enthused by our talking points, but some have commented that our messaging does not align directly enough with the government's priorities. While Coalition members list past innovations that were born out of astronomy, it may be wise to tailor our key points and describe how funding astronomy would mean concretely addressing governmental and societal priorities such as job creation, economic growth and diversification, and STEM education.

One recent event of note led by the Coalition was an astronomy reception on Parliament Hill in May 2019. Following a meeting with NDP MP, Hlne Laverdire, the Coalition received an invitation to host an event that allowed Canadian astronomers to showcase current and future astronomy projects to MPs in an engaging, informal and interactive environment. Several projects were featured, many of which had virtual reality experiences: CAS-TOR, JWST, SKA, TMT, CHIME and the Maunakea Observatories. The event was relatively well attended and the feedback the Coalition received was positive. That being said, this effort was mostly led by CASCA members on a volunteer-basis with the help of Temple Scott Associates on a short timeline. Future such events, if there are any, may require more support to increase their impact and visibility.

3.2.1 Don't Let Go Canada

One remarkably successful lobbying initiative in the space sector was the Don't Let Go Canada campaign led by the Aerospace Industries Association of Canada and MDA, Canada's largest space company. The campaign involved a petition which amassed nearly 6000 signatures to the Government of Canada asking for the development of a new space strategy that will secure Canada's place in space and to have that strategy fully funded in the 2019 Budget. The Don't Let Go Canada campaign was also extremely visible online through social media and even bought physical ad space in Ottawa to gain traction near Parliament Hill.

The success of this campaign, which was of course backed by a substantial budget, is undeniable. The Government of Canada announced \$2.05 billion in funding over 24 years for Canada, earmarked to join NASA's Lunar Gateway mission in March 2019. \$150 million over five years is included in the funding specifically dedicated towards the creation of the Lunar Exploration Accelerator Program (LEAP). Its goals include a strong interlinked partnership transcending across small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), together with academia, while embracing cornerstone domains leveraging artificial intelligence, namely in areas of health and life sciences robotics for space applications for the benefits of Canadians. One of the campaign's strengths was the sheer number of companies, universities and institutes (68) seemingly speaking with a united voice. Messaging also centred around national pride ("Canada is a world leader in space tech, help secure our place in space"), how space affects the daily lives of Canadians and economic growth thanks to the space industry. While the resulting funding from Don't Let Go Canada may not be perfectly aligned with the goals of the Coalition for Canadian Astronomy, there are a number of interesting lessons our community can learn from this successful exercise:

- It is indeed possible to obtain government funding for space exploration in Canada.
- The current key policy issue that must be leveraged when presenting a project to MPs for funding is the economy. Job creation is paramount in Canada at the moment.
- While messaging doesn't have to be specific — general support can be requested rather than support for very specific projects — it must be clear and relatable.
- A strategic communications plan is incredibly beneficial in getting messaging across. Attaching it to popular outreach initiatives (e.g. CSA's Junior Astronauts program), using eye-catching imagery and slogans and involving well-known advocates (e.g. Chris Hadfield) should be explored whenever possible.

4 Moving Forward

Building off initiatives that already exist in Canada, there are a number of activities that could be promoted throughout our community that would better ensure astronomy advocacy and engagement in the context of our current society. We present an overview of these ideas here.

Broadly, our community's approach to EPO has been reactive rather than proactive. This is not surprising given the resources (both in time and money) at our disposition to design and deliver our activities. We hope that outreach initiatives such as those presented here can be incorporated into astronomy research projects at the **conception** phase. We also believe that some of the structural recommendations we present will help make this easier to implement.

4.1 Astronomers as Advocates and Storytellers

So many astronomer origin stories are linked to specific moments they lived or people they met, often during their childhood. And many scientists started down the path of science through the doorway that is astronomy. As astronomers, it is our duty to cultivate a sense of wonder and curiosity about the Universe in those around us. While there is often a will to do so, members of our community often find themselves held back from engaging more with the public either due to a lack of time or a sense of unease at being able to connect with the public skillfully. Despite this, a recent poll of CASCA members by the CASCA EPO committee demonstrated that CASCA members both believe in the importance of and participate in EPO activities. These grassroots efforts are an incredible strength that cannot be replicated by one or a few individuals working full-time on national EPO projects; rather they should absolutely be leveraged and amplified by CASCA.

While developing research skills is of course fundamental for undergraduate and graduate students, it is becoming increasingly obvious that communication skills are also exceedingly useful to a student's path and ensures they will be better advocates for astronomy and more engaging scientists for the general public. As such, we believe workshops related to science communication should be more incorporated to the courses offered in physics and astronomy departments across Canada. Alternatively, resources should be made available for students to participate in similar workshops organised by outreach organisations. Such opportunities should also be made readily available to astronomers at all stages of their careers.

While astronomy is a science that is relatively uncontroversial when compared to climate change, genetics and other scientific fields, some members of the general public and many politicians will sometimes ask why we should be investing in the understanding of the Universe. As previously mentioned, beyond stimulating the public's curiosity about space, showcasing the impacts of astronomy in the daily lives of Canadian citizens is one of the best ways to get them interested in astronomy, make them appreciate the importance of the innovation it brings and, importantly, convince them that it is worth investing in astronomy. Many astronomers find themselves unable to answer questions related to the daily applications of astronomy. The creation and dissemination of resources such as booklets, infographics or "cheatsheets" by our community would serve the role of educating the public on the benefits of astronomy to society and would also turn us all into better equipped advocates for our science. The International Astronomical Union (IAU) recently published an online booklet titled "Astronomy in Everyday Life"

that could be more widely distributed across our community. A version that emphasises Canadian contributions to useful astronomy technology spinoffs would likely be even more appreciated by the Canadian public. The recent online platform SpaceMatters.ca, which was in part funded by an NSERC PromoScience grant, serves a similar purpose for space exploration and could be re-used, emulated or expanded upon for the astronomy community.

The importance of making astronomers better, more trusted storytellers goes beyond the good it can do for our own community. As explained in Sect. 4 of Matzner et al.'s white paper, *Astronomy in a Low-Carbon Future*, "astronomers are among the scientists most frequently in direct contact with the general public, and we reach many non-scientists with introductory astronomy (Astro-101) courses". This public exposure and our basic knowledge of atmospheric physics leads us to often being asked questions related to the incredibly important (and unfortunately controversial) topic of climate change. It is our duty to use our platform to advocate for better understanding and, ultimately, positive change for this topic. Improving our relationship with the general public allows us to be even better and more effective actors for this positive change in our society.

4.2 Making Astronomy Inclusive

Experiments have shown that the general public's perception of a scientist is heavily skewed towards a single portrait: a white man. This is especially concerning when this biased view of a scientist is shown in children who rely on models they can relate to in order to consider pursuing certain career paths. An obvious way to counter this issue is by ensuring that the astronomers brought into the spotlight to engage with the public span a diversity of genders and races. Canada's demographics are more diverse than ever before, and the astronomical community must mirror this lest we grow the divide between the average Canadian and what is perceived to be the average Canadian astronomer. Furthermore, closing this gap makes it considerably easier for children to imagine themselves as scientists later on, as it counteracts the popular belief that science is reserved for individuals that are born with a certain level of intelligence. Rather, in sharing our stories, it is important to emphasise acquired characteristics such as curiosity, perseverance and teamwork that has allowed us to perform our research. In addition to this, there is considerable merit in harnessing the multitude of student-based organisations across the country in various universities, such as local astronomy clubs, together with nonprofit and non-governmental organisation.

The advent of citizen science has also been remarkable in bridging the gap between the public and scientists as we allow the public to *become* the scientist in these instances. Projects such as Galaxy Zoo and Planet Hunters have not only proved fruitful scientifically — a number of scientific discoveries were made thanks to the contributions of "amateur" scientists — but have also lifted the veil on how real astronomy research is done. We strongly endorse such endeavours and encourage the active participation of Canadian citizens in astronomy research through the creation of more citizen science projects.

4.3 EPO as a Funding Agency Priority

As it stands, many funding agencies that Canadian astronomers rely on such as NSERC and CFI put little to no importance on applicants' EPO activities in their evaluation metrics. Worse yet, agencies such as CFI specifically state that no money awarded to successful applicants may be spent on EPO activities, yet the dissemination of these funded projects' results are extremely valuable in the quest to enrich Canada's science culture.

NSERC's PromoScience program does give out grants for EPO projects, but these are specifically targeted towards K-12 education, leave out the general public and are still more often awarded to informal education centres than to scientific institutions. A promising new program called DIALOGUE was launched this year by the Fonds de recherche du Québec (FQR) which will award money directly to scientists developing projects that disseminate their research to the general public. As this program is only available to researchers in the province of Quebec, we hope federal funding agencies follow suit to allow researchers across Canada to showcase their work and help the public better connect to science through their research. We also note that the National Science Foundation (NSF) have added a "Broader Impacts Review Criterion" to their merit review of proposals which folds in education, outreach and societal impacts of research projects. This shows that the NSF recognises the importance of the dissemination of results beyond the scientific team working on the funded project, and we hope Canadian funding

agencies can soon come to the same conclusion.

The recent addition of equity, diversity and inclusion in evaluation metrics at all levels of funding agencies throughout Canada show that such a change can be instilled if pressure is applied and a general shift in societal priorities is felt. With the increasing presence and awareness of “fake news” and the like in the media, we believe that it is the right time to strongly encourage Canadian funding agencies to include EPO considerations in their grant programs.

4.4 Leveraging Museums and Science Centres

According to Carty et al. (2014), Canadians rank 2nd (out of 29 polled countries) for their interest in visiting science centres: 32% of respondents had visited one in the past year. Over 400 science outreach initiatives related to museums, science centres, zoos and aquariums were reported. Carty et al. (2014) states that the “success of Canada’s network of science centres and museums is reflected in their strong international reputations and relatively high numbers of annual visitors.” This large network and massive visitorship represents a remarkable and underutilised resource for astronomers to reach audiences they may not typically have access to.

There are several initiatives across the country that bring scientists into museums (e.g. “Curiosity on Stage” at Ottawa’s Canada Science and Technology Museum, “Research Live!” at the Ontario Science Centre in Toronto) to take advantage of this outreach platform. This direct engagement with the public will help close the divide between science and society, and the more informal setting of the interaction (versus a university lecture hall) humanizes astronomers making them much more approachable; evidence shows this attenuates the feeling of alienation the public often feels towards scientists (Olson, 2009).

We encourage members of our community to reach out to their local museums, science centres, planetariums or others to initiate collaborations. Involvement can be as small as giving a public talk once or as large as acting as a regular consultant to ensure the veracity and timeliness of space facts and astronomical discoveries featured in the science centre’s displays and shows.

Further, we recommend a more deliberate collaboration between the members of the CASCA Board and the Canadian Association of Science Centres (CASC), beginning with a or several members of the CASCA Board or EPO Committee attending the CASC Annual Conference. Likewise, CASCA should invite local science centre professionals to join the CASCA annual conference’s EPO day.

4.5 Leveraging the Media

According to Carty et al. (2014), 93% of polled Canadians were moderately to very interested in new scientific discoveries and technological developments, which ranks Canada 1st out of 33 polled countries. Clearly, there is a thirst for science news in our country. Canadians rely on traditional media and increasingly on the internet to consume science stories. Having Canadian stories highlighted in the media is particularly appreciated and helps develop a sense of pride in our national astronomy culture. Given that science journalists are now few and far between and are generally overwhelmed and overworked, it is imperative that astronomers do their part to communicate their discoveries to journalists in an effective way.

We encourage the Canadian astronomy community to form better ties with their institutions’ press officers and communications departments to help in the creation and dissemination of press releases related to important scientific results. Furthermore, if their newsworthy scientific results are based on data taken from specific facilities (e.g. CFHT, Gemini, Space Telescope Science Institute, JPL, etc.), we encourage them to contact these facilities as they often have the resources necessary to help write press releases. Astronomy institutes that have the resources to do so are encouraged to invest in their outreach/communications/press officers whose duties include the promotion of important scientific results to the general public and the media. Finally, we believe that having a paid CASCA Press Officer would be beneficial to our entire community. Such a role could be folded into a larger position that includes other tasks such as EPO, budget planning, administration, etc. The American Astronomical Society (AAS) has had great success publicising its members’ scientific achievements through the existence of such a role. We acknowledge that the creation of such a position, be it standalone or as part of a broader EPO/Admin position,

would require either an increase in CASCA membership fees or exploring alternate means of funding which could include philanthropy, donations or working with a fundraising professional. The Royal Astronomical Society of Canada (RASC) recently hired a Youth Outreach Coordinator for a three-year term thanks to funds given to them by the Trottier Family Foundation. Furthermore, they have put together a Fundraising Committee to help with all their initiatives that require financial backing.

5 Conclusions

While the state of science culture in Canada is relatively healthy especially compared to other developed nations, evidence of skepticism and erosion in the public's trust in scientists seen in Western countries is unfortunately still reported. Furthermore, our community is grappling with often unreliable funding sources and the absence of a process which allows the granting of funding to big science projects. This is resulting in several missed opportunities in terms of Canadian-lead projects that are dying on the vine or having to bow out of collaborations with international partners. In this white paper, we presented a number of past advocacy and engagement initiatives that have attempted to increase and improve our visibility with the public, and we submit a number of recommendations we hope will continue raising the standards of astronomy EPO in our community.

5.1 LRP2020 Recommendations

- We recommend that CASCA hire a **paid** Press Officer that can assist CASCA members in disseminating their scientific results to the public and the media and help connect astronomers to science journalists across Canada and internationally. This position could be a part-time task folded into a full-time position that encompasses other duties (national EPO activities, administration, etc.) and would require increasing CASCA membership fees and/or exploring alternate means of funding (philanthropy, donations, fundraising, etc.). The duties of such a Press/EPO Officer could include the development resources such as workshops and cheat sheets that would enable astronomers to become better science communicators and advocates for Canadian astronomy and its societal benefits.
- We recommend that physics and astronomy departments across Canada incorporate “soft skills” such as science communication and public speaking into their graduate curricula.
- We recommend that the Coalition for Canadian Astronomy work closely with CASCA to develop and deliver a broader suite of astronomy advocacy and lobbying events on Parliament Hill.
- We recommend that CASCA and its Board work on more deliberate collaborations between CASCA and science centres as well as between CASCA and student astronomy clubs. This would include sending one or several CASCA members to the Canadian Association of Science Centres' annual conference, and inviting science centre professionals and members of astronomy student clubs to the EPO session of CASCA's annual meeting.
- We recommend that federal funding agencies such as NSERC and CFI include EPO activities in their evaluation metrics and allow a portion of awarded funding to be used for EPO and communication activities.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

We propose several initiatives that would allow more public support and financial backing of astronomy research projects that would, themselves, result in advances in our understanding of the Universe.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

This white paper mainly deals with national advocacy and EPO matters for which only the Canadian community is involved. That being said, our recommendations would position the Canadian community as a stronger and more reliable international partner that would allow for Canadian leadership on all fronts.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

CASCA members and Canadian astronomers more broadly have already shown that they believe and participate in EPO initiatives. We are merely presenting guidelines in the hopes of leveraging the incredible grassroots efforts already shown by our community.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

If implemented, we believe that our recommendations would help secure future opportunities for many decades for Canadian astronomy across all sub-fields through increased public support and funding.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The costs for our proposed initiatives are relatively low, they are simply not prioritised at the moment. We believe that investing in these initiatives now will pay off in the longterm by increasing available funds for both EPO initiatives and astronomy research projects.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

Yes, our white paper extensively covers the broader impacts of astronomy and recommends initiatives on how we can communicate these impacts to Canadian citizens. Furthermore, they are meant to increase science literacy in Canada, make science more inclusive, address EDI failings in STEM fields and encourage youth to choose STEM careers.

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